

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF Al_2O_3/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The tensile properties, fracture toughness and hardness of two random short fibre composites, $Al_2O_3/Al7Si0.6Mg$ and $Al_2O_3/Al5Si3Cu1Mg$, have been studied. With respect to the matrix properties, they exhibit the increases in modulus, hardness and work hardening rate. The tension strength is not so improved, the plasticity and fracture toughness are low. Work-hardening law of the composites obeys Hollomon relation. The harder the matrix, the greater the increase in hardness and work-hardening rate. The main reason for a low K_{Ic} is because matrix plastic deformation was limited by fibres. Matrix property is more important to most of the mechanical properties for a random short fibre composite.

Keywords: Composite, Alumina fibre, cast aluminium alloy, mechanical property

INTRODUCTION

Driven by the need to build lighter weight, quieter, more fuel efficient engines, the technology which has been established to selectively reinforce pistons for advanced diesel engines is now being applied to other components such as the connecting rod, piston pin, cylinderliner and various areas of the cylinder head and valve train(1-2).

One of the main barriers to the use of metal matrix composite (MMC) in engineering applications is that they are more brittle than unreinforced metals, as apparent in the low elongations to tensile failure, and the low fracture toughness values frequently measured on these materials (3), for example, fracture toughness values for unreinforced aluminium alloys are in the range of 25-40 $MPa\sqrt{m}$, while the composites have plane strain values of 7-25 $MPa\sqrt{m}$. The reasons of this drop in toughness has not been understood very well. On the other hand, there is still dispute in evaluating a valid K_{Ic} for discontinuous reinforcements MMC. Most tests did not strictly follow ASTM procedures, however, most test results were considered to be valid. K.Hirana and T.Sasaki (4) reported that the fracture toughness of SiCw/7075 composites decreased with increasing whisker volume fraction, and the fibre orientation to loads had a strong effect on its apparent K_{Ic} .

At present, the mechanical property of short fibre MMC is difficultly predicted. S.J Harris and T.E.Wilks(5) reported the tensile properties at room temperature (R.T.) for short alumina fiber reinforced Al (99.85%) (LMO) and its alloy (Al-Cu-Mg-Ni) (2618A), their results showed that fibers had brought about an increase in both elastic modulus(20%) and the level of matrix work hardening. The tensile strength of the LMO was increased by the presence of the fibers, whilst that of 2618A alloy was impaired. S.J.Girot (6) et al reported some mechanical properties of SiC short fibers reinforced $Al7Si0.6Mg$ composite. Their results showed that the tensile strength at R.T. was not improved, however, the tensile strength at elevated temperature was improved. On the contrary,

C.Masuda's (7) research results on 10-20Vol.% SiCw/A2024 composite showed that its tensile strength was improved very much, and in good agreement with rule of mixture (ROM). C.M.Friend (8) analyzed theoretically the effect of matrix properties on reinforcement efficiency of short alumina fiber/aluminium composites. Probably, the above contrary results are caused by different processing.

In conclusion, although there are already some investigations on short fiber MMCs, it is difficult to predict and improve all their performances. In this paper, the tensile property, fracture toughness and hardness of alumina short fibre reinforced two cast aluminium alloy composites are studied, as for their fatigue behaviour has already been reported elsewhere (9). Here, the attention will be focused on the comparison of the effect of matrix property on mechanical property.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two random short fiber composites, $Al_2O_3/Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg$ and $Al_2O_3/Al_7Si_0.6Mg$ (in wt%), have been studied. The reinforcement is SAFFIL Al_2O_3 short fibers (grade RF), their average length and diameter are $150\mu m$ and $3\mu m$ respectively. The mechanical properties are given in Table 1. The composites with fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 20% were manufactured by squeeze casting. Typical fibre orientation in the composites is shown in Fig.1. After casting, the composites were subsequently applied the following heat treatments:

6 hrs. at $510^\circ C$ + water quench ($70^\circ C$) + 6 hrs. at $160^\circ C$, for $Al_2O_3/Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg$.

6 hrs. at $540^\circ C$ + water quench + 6 hrs. at $160^\circ C$, for $Al_2O_3/Al_7Si_0.6Mg$.

The specimen configuration and dimension for tension tests are given in Fig.2. An extensometer was used to measure strain. Load-elongation curves were recorded by a conventional X-Y recorder. The machine is an INSTRON 115. Cross-head speed was 0.5 mm/min . Elastic modulus, ultimate tension strength (U.S.T.), 0.2% proof stress, strain to failure and work hardening exponent were determined by the load-elongation curves.

The vickers hardness of two composites and matrixes were determined with a hardmeter (MAB) to assess their resistance to plastic deformation. The employed load was 10 kg, the time holding the load was 20 seconds. Because the sizes of all the indenter diagonals ($500\mu m$) were large enough relative to fiber length ($150\mu m$) and diameter ($3\mu m$), datum scatter is therefore small. Microhardness of the fibres was determined by a microhardness hardometer (SOPELEM) to try to understand the relation between hardness of composites and those of their components. The load and the time holding the load were 20 g and 30 seconds respectively.

Fig.1. Typical fibre orientation of the composites 500x

Fig.2. Specimen configuration for tension tests

Fracture toughness tests were carried out as the standard test method for plane-strain fracture toughness of metallic materials (ASTM E399-83). The standard single edge-notched specimens for three points bend test were used. Specimen dimensions and crack plane orientation in specimens are shown in Fig.3. Loading speed was $10N/sec$. No fatigue crack was made because: (1) it has been shown that below a certain machined notch radius, around 30-50 microns, a cut pre-notch yields the same results as fatigue pre-cracking (10-13); (2) our results would be compared with Davidson's, the author of reference (14), in his study a fatigue crack of 1mm were made for the same materials.

In order to precisely determinate crack initiation loads, a video tape recording system with magnification of 200 times was used for recording crack stable growth and rapid fracture. Some polished specimens were loaded with an increase of 20N after loads had been over 700 N, then unloaded and periodically removed to an optic microscope for observing crack growth after each increased load.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

All the obtained mechanical properties for the two composites are summarised in Table 1, which are the average of at least four specimens.

Table.1.mean mechanical properties of the composites, matrices and fibre

	Al ₂ O ₃ /Al ₇ Si _{0.6} Mg	Al ₂ O ₃ /Al ₅ Si ₃ Cu ₁ Mg
U.T.S. (MPa)		
composite	286	378
matrix	317	392
fibre	2000	2000
0.2% yield strength (MPa)		
composite	220	378*
matrix	130	301
modulus (GPa)		
composite	94	102
matrix	72	72
fibre	300	300
strain to failure(%)		
composite	0.95	0.65
matrix	1.9	1.0
fibre	0.67	0.67
toughness(MPa√m)		
composite K _{IC}		15.3
composite K _Q	11.3	
composite K _{Q'}	13.1, 12.1**	15.3, 13.2**
hardness (Hv):		
composite	108	197
fibre	1352	1355
matrix	92	135
work-hardening exponent		
composite	0.33	0.60

* only one specimen had plastic deformation over 0.2%. ** they are presented by Davidson.

K_{IC} and K_Q are calculated by valid loads as indicated in the standard test method of ASTM E399-83. K_{Q'} is calculated by maximum load.

1. Hardness

It was reported that hardness of unidirectional alumina fibre-Al composites is proportional to V_f , and its transverse hardness is much lower than longitudinal hardness(2).The first fact means that hardness of the composite can be expressed by ROM,the second fact means that composite hardness depends on fibre orientation. Hardness of two composites in Table 1 being compared, it can be seen that the hardness of Al₂O₃/Al₅Si₃Cu₁Mg is increased 46%, while that of Al₂O₃/Al₇Si_{0.6}Mg is increased only 22% with respect to their matrixes, in other words, the softer the matrix, the less its hardness increment; however, according to ROM, the result should be opposite to this. That is to say if ROM is used for composite hardness, it should be modified by both a fibre orientation factor and a matrix hardness factor. When randomly oriented short fibre composite is compressed by an indenter, both fibres and matrix support the loads, but the proportions of the loads supported by fibres and matrix depend on matrix hardness, the harder the matrix into which fibres are insetted, the greater the proportion of the load supported by fibres. That is the reason why the reinforcement efficiency in hardness of Al₂O₃/Al₅Si₃Cu₁Mg is higher than that of Al₂O₃/Al₇Si_{0.6}Mg.

2. Tensile property

Tension test results given in Table 1. show that, in comparison those of matrices alone, mean elastic modulus of the composites have been increased by a factor of 33%. The strains to failure have been decreased; their U.T.S. values are not improved, taking Al7Si0.6Mg matrix composite as an example, strain to failure is decreased from 1.9% to 0.9%; and matrix U.T.S. is 317 MPa, while that of the composite is 286 MPa.

It is always true that the elastic modulus of MMC is increased by ceramic reinforcement, whether their other mechanical properties are improved or not. At the present time, quality of most MMC is not stable owing to the difficulty in fabrication technique, in this case, elastic modulus of MMC is not influenced very much, it follows that the elastic modulus of MMC is not sensitive to material microstructure, and ceramic reinforcements in MMC always resist its metallic matrix deforming no matter of its microstructure, and hence, result in an increased rigidity of MMC.

It is well known that longitudinal strain to failure for a continuous fibre MMC is dominated by brittle fibres, and close to that of the fibres. Evidently, for short fibre reinforced MMC, both matrix and fibres dominate its strain to failure because some parts of matrix can deform freely, which is favorable to plasticity of MMC. For the same matrix, an increase in V_f decreases its plasticity, and at a given V_f , good matrix plasticity can lead to not bad plasticity of MMC. It has been proved that great deformation in particulates reinforced MMC was concentrated in the region where particulates were enriched and cracks passed by, in the region remote to the regions depicted, deformation was small (13), that is to say that the plasticity of the matrix have not be developed up, perhaps, this is one of the reasons why plasticity of ceramic reinforcement MMC is often poor.

It is difficult to precisely calculate the strength of a random short fiber composite, as an approximation, there is such a formula, i.e. so called ROM modified:

$$\sigma_c = n_o n_1 \sigma_f V_f + \sigma'_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

where n_1 is the fibre length factor, n_o fibre orientation factor, V_f fibre volume fraction, σ_c , σ_f and σ'_m are respectively the strength of composite, that of fiber and stress supported by matrix when the composite fractures. The orientation factor n_o is varied from 0.2 to 1 depending on the fiber orientation in the composite. For random short fiber composite fabricated by squeeze-casting, $n_o = 0.2$, which is corresponding to a quasi-isotropic material (15). The length factor n_1 can be expressed by:

$$n_1 = \begin{cases} 1 & L \gg L_c \\ 1 - L_c/2L & L > L_c \\ L/2L_c & L < L_c \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where L : fiber real length, L_c : fiber critical length expressed by equation (3):

$$L_c = \frac{\sigma_f d_f}{2 \tau_i} \quad (3)$$

in which d_f is fiber diameter, τ_i interface shear strength. Evidently both fiber real length and its critical length are important. It has been proved that if fiber real length is as five times as the critical length, the reinforcement efficiency in tensile strength can approach to 90% for unidirectionally reinforced short fiber MMC (15). For the composites used in our investigation, the fibre critical length is about 20 μm , which is evaluated approximately by expression (3), therefore, the length factor is 1 according to expression (2).

Using $\sigma_f = 2000$ MPa, and $\sigma'_m = 250$ MPa for Al7Si0.6Mg matrix composite, and $\sigma'_m = 380$ MPa for Al5Si3Cu1Mg matrix composite, we can obtain their U.T.S. by expression (1): 280 MPa and 384 MPa respectively, they are very close to experimental results in table 1. The initial alloys are not reinforced by the fibres with respect to their original U.T.S., which is because of a small orientation factor (0.2), and therefore the critical fibre volume fraction (V_{fc}) for this kind of composite, expressed by equation (4), is much greater than that of an unidirectional composite:

$$V_{fc} = \frac{\sigma_m - \sigma'_m}{n_o n_1 \sigma_f - \sigma'_m} \quad (4)$$

According to equation (4) and the data, the V_{fe} values are 45% and 60% for $Al_2O_3/Al_7Si_0.6Mg$ and $Al_2O_3/Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg$ respectively, that means that it is difficult to greatly increase the R.T. tensile strength of a random short fiber MMC, even though MMC with a high V_f is fabricated, its real strength can be hardly increased with V_f when V_f is over 30. Since orientation factor is very small, the reinforcement role of the fibre is very small too, hence, the contribution from matrix to composite strength is important.

Typical fitting results for work hardening behaviour are given in expression (5) and (6) :

$$\text{for } Al_2O_3/Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg, \quad \text{Log}\sigma = 3.88 + 0.60 \text{ Log}\epsilon \quad R=0.99 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{for } Al_2O_3/Al_7Si_0.6Mg, \quad \text{Log}\sigma = 3.21 + 0.33 \text{ Log}\epsilon \quad R=1.00 \quad (6)$$

where σ : true stress, ϵ : true strain, and R : correlation coefficient. From the expressions it can be seen that the work hardening exponents are 0.60 and 0.33 for $Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg$ and $Al_7Si_0.6Mg$ composites respectively, while that for aluminium alloy is about 0.15. Evidently, the introduction of the fibres brings about a great increase in work hardening rate, and $Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg$ composite is more easy to be work-hardened. The correlation coefficients for each fitting are very close to 1, that is to say that the work hardening behaviour of the matrixes for the composites obeys the Hollomon relation very well. The above results show that matrix nature has an important effect on tension property of this class of composites, as is concluded in Fig.4, from which it can be seen that composite plasticity (Fig.4a), work-hardening rate (Fig.4b) and macroscopic aspect of fracture surfaces (Fig.4c) are dominated by matrix property.

Fig.3. KIC specimen dimensions and its crack plane orientation

a). Stress-strain curves

b).work hardening behaviour: $\sigma = \sigma_0 \epsilon^n$, n is 0.60 for $Al_2O_3/Al_5Si_3Cu_1Mg$ and 0.33 for $Al_2O_3/Al_7Si_0.6Mg$

c).fracture surface aspects x8

Fig.4.comparison on tensile test behaviour of the composites

3. Toughness

The obtained fracture toughness values are also summarized in Table 1 in which Davidson's are given for comparison. Evidently, the difference between our and his results is small. According to standard of ASTM E399, the obtained results for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al7Si0.6Mg}$ are invalid, but only KQ value because thickness of these specimens is less than $2.5(K_{Ic}/\sigma_{0.2})^2$, and P_{max}/P_Q did not exceed 1.1, where P_{max} and P_Q are maximum and valid loads respectively. However, the fracture surfaces evidenced only a very small shear lip for these specimens (Fig.5a), the measured values should approximate those for plane strain. Recorded videos and metallography observation during the tests

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al7Si0.6Mg}$ 5.6 x $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al5Si3Cu1Mg}$ 6x
a). fracture surface aspects

b). load-displacement curves

c). Plastic deformation near crack in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al7Si0.6Mg}$ and d). in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al5Si3Cu1Mg}$
Fig.5. Comparison on fracture toughness test results of two composites

have showed that there was no stable growth of the crack even loading rate was very slow (5N/sec.), all the specimens were failed at once, when the load arrived a maximum value. Therefore, real valid loads should be maximum loads which are greater than those determined by the standard method, therefore, KQ calculated by real valid loads are greater than KQ in the table. By contrast, all the results for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al5Si3Cu1Mg}$ are valid according to the same standard. In recorded load-displacement curves, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al7Si0.6Mg}$ showed a obvious plastic deformation, while $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al5Si3Cu1Mg}$ composites had hardly plastic deformation (Fig.5b.).

It is well known that in small scale yield the plastic zone size r_p is expressed by :

$$r_p = C(K_I/\sigma_y)^2 \quad (7)$$

where C is a constant about 0.1 in plane strain, 0.3 in plane stress, K_I , stress density factor for the crack of mode I, and σ_y , yield stress. Metallographic observations on the polished specimen surfaces showed that plastic zone near the tip of the crack at K_{Ic} extends about 210 microns for

Al7Si0.6Mg composite, 98 microns for Al5Si3Cu1Mg composites, if we define the plastic zone as such a region where total deformation has arrived the strain to failure of the fibre , i.e. the region where fibres are broken, which is corresponding to 0.27% plastic deformation for the composites after minus average elastic deformation of 0.4%. The plastic zone size at the same condition for cast aluminium alloys ranges from 400 to 700µm. Evidently, the plastic zone size for MMC is decreased because fibres limited plastic deformation of the matrix, and thereby increased σ_y . The plastic zone sizes of 264 microns for Al₂O₃/Al7Si0.6Mg, and 164 microns for Al₂O₃/Al5Si3Cu1Mg are calculated, using equation (7), KQ or KIC and yield stress in table 1, they are a little greater than the observed values. Two materials, Al₂O₃/Al7Si0.6Mg and Al₂O₃/Al5Si3Cu1Mg, being compared, it can be seen that plastic zone of the former (Fig.5c) is much larger than that of the latter (Fig.5d.). The most significant contributions to fracture energy in metal materials is from plastic deformation, therefore, plastic zone size is important to fracture toughness. The fracture toughness of Al₂O₃/Al7Si0.6Mg are closed to those of Al₂O₃/Al5Si3Cu1Mg because of its better plasticity. On the other hand, a higher work hardening exponent of the latter has beneficial effect on its fracture toughness, hence compensates the detriment influence from its poor plasticity.

Owing to heterogeneous microstructure in short fibre MMC, stress state in the composite is complex, even the specimen is loaded uniaxially, there can be shear stress in some parts, and hence fracture manner is probably a mixed mode combined mode I, II and III cracks together, for instance, a short mode II crack can be seen from figure 6., in this case, the stress density factor for a single crack mode such as KI, is difficult to be determined by classic method. To avoid this problem, it will be better to study their fracture toughness from the point of view of energy .

Fig.6. A short crack in mode II 23 x

For a composite, the total fracture energy expended in enlarging the crack a unit area (G_c), is made of the sum of the work consumed in the plastic deformation surrounding the crack (W_p), and energies consumed in forming new surfaces which include those of fibre fracture (γ_f), interface failure (γ_i) and matrix fracture (γ_{mc}), i.e.:

$$G_c = W_{pc} + 2(\gamma_f + \gamma_i + \gamma_{mc}) \quad (8)$$

For the unreinforced initial metal material, there is a similar equation:

$$G_o = W_{po} + 2 \gamma_{mo} \quad (9)$$

where the subscripts o is used for distinguishing the corresponding items in expression (8). The difference of the fracture energy between the composite and its initial alloy, ΔG , can be written as:

$$\Delta G = \Delta W_p + \Delta \gamma \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta W_p = W_{pc} - W_{po}$, $\Delta \gamma = 2(\gamma_f + \gamma_i + \gamma_{mc}) - 2\gamma_{mo}$. Because the plastic zone of MMC is decreased by brittle fibres, and most of the plastic deformation are mainly concentrated near reinforcements (13), the plastic work is decreased too, ΔW_p for MMC reinforced by ceramic reinforcements is always negative; and therefore, ΔG depends upon the second item. In general, interface fracture energy γ_i can not be over that of the matrix γ_{mo} because if the interface bond strength is higher than the matrix strength, it is matrix that is failed. According to Cooper(16), fibre

pull work is small. However, it is possible that fracture energy of a ceramic fibre γ_f is higher than that of the matrix, due to their strong ionic bond. In conclusion, the second item $\Delta\gamma \geq 0$, mainly depending on fibre fracture energy. If $\Delta\gamma > |\Delta W_p|$ ($|\Delta W_p|$ represents the absolute value of ΔW_p), in other words, if fracture energy of the fibres is far greater than that of the matrix, so that it can compensate plasticity work loss, then $\Delta G > 0$, the fracture toughness of MMC can be improved and increased with V_f , which has proved for B/Al composites (17). If $\Delta\gamma \leq |\Delta W_p|$, then $\Delta G \leq 0$, it is impossible to improve the fracture toughness of MMC. In fact, at present, the fracture toughness for most of MMC is often far lower than those of their initial alloys as summarized in reference (3). Even though there are many factors influencing the fracture toughness of MMC, however, the above cause is the main one of them.

CONCLUSIONS

The two random short fiber composites exhibit reinforcement effects in modulus and hardness. Their work hardening rates are increased greatly. However, the plasticity and fracture toughness are low. R.T. tension strengths are not improved. For most of the mechanical properties of random short fiber MMCs, matrix performance is more important relative to unidirectional MMC. However, its fracture toughness is not sensitive to the matrix properties.

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